

PROCESSING OF RECYCLABLE ALL-PP COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: In spite of its good intrinsic properties, Polypropylene (PP) has to be reinforced for engineering applications. Glass fibre is the main reinforcing element of polypropylene. Unfortunately glass fibre/PP systems cause problems for recycling whereas an all-PP concept, polypropylene based reinforcement in a polypropylene matrix will be easy to recycle. The challenge in all-PP concept is to find a processing window, which is large enough to keep the oriented PP tape or fibre intact while this is impregnated with a PP resin. The technological breakthrough in processing of all-PP composites, which has been established, is based on welding of co-extruded tapes. They consist of an oriented homopolymer core which provides strength and stiffness and a copolymer skin with a lower melting temperature. These tapes are woven into fabrics, which can be stacked and consolidated in a hot-press or belt-press into flat laminates. Consolidation is achieved by simply welding the tapes/ fabrics together, thus avoiding typical impregnation problems encountered in traditional thermoplastic composite manufacturing. Young's modulus of unidirectional composites varies between 5 and 15 GPa with strength up to 500 MPa. This development will be the basis for revolutionary mono-materials products for environmental safety. By replacing glass fibres by high-performance PP tapes, true "all-PP" products can be designed based on PP resin, -fibres, -foams and honeycombs such as 100% polypropylene sandwich panels. This paper describes the use of all-PP concept in traditional composite manufacturing processes such as filament winding, thermoforming, short "tape" composites and sandwich constructions.

KEYWORDS: All-Polypropylene, Sustainable, Stamping, Sandwich, Pipes.

INTRODUCTION

A new era has come to consumer goods manufacturers: sustainable product development and the concept of Eco-design. Consumer awareness and environmental legislation exhort the automotive industry among others to design any car component to be fully recyclable. In the European Union, a new directive from October 2000, the End-of-Life-Vehicle (ELV) enforces that by 2015 cars must be made of 95% by weight of recyclable materials, of which 85% can be recovered through reuse or mechanical recycling and only 10% through energy recovery or thermal recycling. Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEM) and their suppliers are making increasing use of recyclable materials. Most of the materials used in a car nowadays can be classified in one of these 6 materials families: steel, polyolefins, aluminium, glass, elastomers and polyurethane. Polypropylene (PP) as a polyolefin, is one of the easiest polymer to recycle which led PP to penetrate largely the automotive plastics market. However PP has to be reinforced for engineering applications. Glass fibre is its main reinforcement because it is cheap with excellent mechanical properties. But full recovery of an end of life vehicle requires easy dismantling and separation of the different recyclable materials such as glass and PP. It is a quasi-impossible task in the case of glass fibre reinforced PP which causes recycling problem both mechanically and thermally.

Recent research proposed to replace glass reinforcement by oriented polypropylene. The University of Leeds, UK, [1, 2] developed the hot compaction process of highly oriented PP tapes or fibres. The surface of the oriented material is melted under suitable conditions of pressure and temperature and will become the matrix of the laminate. A disadvantage of this technique is however that the

processing window is very narrow. Peijs *et al.* [3, 4] introduced a different approach for all-PP composite material where the highly oriented tapes are manufactured by co-extrusion. Co-extruded tapes of an oriented homopolymer core, which provides strength and stiffness and a PP copolymer skin with a lower melting temperature. A broad processing window is achieved by a melting temperature difference between the skin and the core. This difference is not only due to the lower melting temperature of the copolymer but also to the higher molecular orientation of the core [5]. Because the matrix (copolymer PP) is extruded together with reinforcement (PP homopolymer), reinforcement manufacturing and matrix impregnation are achieved in one single step. This is a very different approach compared to the other composites systems whether they are based on thermoset or thermoplastic matrices as they are all based on impregnation processes. Fig. 1 shows the different processing routes to manufacture end products from all-PP tapes that will be described in the present paper. The tapes can be filament wound into pipes or pressure vessels. All-PP woven fabrics of the tape can be belt pressed into flat laminates. The laminates can then be stamped into shell products using a non-isothermal process. Alternatively laminates can be pressed from chopped short tapes. It is also possible to avoid high-investment double belt press process by either stamping directly fabric layers into parts or produce pipes by fabric winding around a removable mandrel. These processes are all suitable for medium to high volume applications.

Fig. 1. All-polypropylene composites from PP pellets to final product

TAPE MANUFACTURING

All-PP tapes are supplied by Lankhorst Indutech BV in the Netherlands (www.pure-composites.com). The tape is 2.2 mm wide and 0.065 mm thick. It is a 3 layers (A-B-A) tape where layer A (5%~3 μ m) is an i-PP copolymer and B is an i-PP homopolymer. Fig. 2 is a cross section of an undrawn tape where the layers A appear black as in this particular case they contain carbon black. The 3 layers (A-B-A) tape is co-extruded. The tape is then drawn in an optimised two stage drawing process so that the homopolymer molecules are highly oriented.

The mechanical properties of the tape are proportional to the molecular orientation, i.e. the draw ratio (λ). Ward [6] reported a maximum draw ratio, λ , up to 20 on a single layer extruded tape corresponding to a E-modulus of 15-20 GPa and a tensile strength of 1 GPa at room temperature. The

all-PP 3 layers tape has a modulus of 15 GPa and strength around 500 MPa (over ten times higher than isotropic PP) while its density is only 0.72 g/cm³. However PP, unlike glass fibres, is a viscoelastic material whose properties are time-temperature dependent. Fig. 3 [7] shows the tensile strength of All-PP tape as a function of temperature. The strain rate used was approximately 150%/min. Tensile strength decreases between room temperature and 150°C. However this degradation of the strength is limited up to 100°C and significant beyond. The strength at 150°C is only about 125 MPa but is still significantly higher than that of isotropic PP at room temperature.

Fig. 2. Tape cross section as extruded

Fig. 3. Tensile strength of All-PP tape

It is also important to note that highly oriented PP fibres or tapes have a negative coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) parallel to the orientation direction. Jawad *et al.* [8] measured a thermal expansion coefficient which increases in absolute value with draw ratio. In addition if the temperature is high enough, shrinkage is permanent at room temperature and involves a loss of both orientation and mechanical properties. But shrinkage reduces with increasing draw ratio [6]. Also constraining the tape can reduce shrinkage either by applying in plane tensile stresses along the drawing direction or, more efficiently, by applying out of plane pressure. Obviously, the required constraining pressure increases with temperature. Hence it is important that the co-extruded tape can be processed at a low temperature in order to retain the properties and allow simpler tooling.

FILAMENT WINDING

Filament winding of all-PP tapes is a low investment and simple processing technique. Co-extruded all-PP tapes can be cold-wound on a mandrel (Fig. 4) and subsequently heated for consolidation. In addition, hoop tensile stresses and radial compressive stresses are generated in the tape because it has a negative CTE and the mandrel a positive one.

**Fig. 4. Cold-winding of all-PP tape
(Courtesy SICOMP, Piteå, Sweden)**

The tensile stresses prevent the tapes to shrink while the compressive ones favour compaction. Neither external compaction pressure nor rotation of the mandrel is required in the oven. It is quite a different process compared to standard thermoplastic filament winding process where the prepreg tapes of the commingled bundle are preheated by hot air, flame or laser local heating before reaching the mandrel. Pressure is usually applied on the contact point [9]. All-PP winding speed is substantially higher as no heating and no cooling is necessary.

Unidirectional plates

This process was used to produce unidirectional (UD) plates. The mandrel, in that particular case, was a thin steel plate. The winding angle was parallel to the “hoop” direction (i.e. at 90° of mandrel axis).

Heating and cooling had to be carried out in a hot press because the singular geometry of the mandrel does not generate any out-of-plane compressive stresses. Heating at 145°C and cooling took place under a constant pressure of 40 bar. Once the steel plate was removed, two UD plates were obtained. The plates were annealed freely for one hour in an oven. Shrinkage as a function of annealing temperature is plotted in Fig. 5. The plates are thermally stable up to 120°C exhibiting a limited shrinkage. After annealing, the residual bending modulus at room temperature was measured. Fig. 6 shows clearly a linear relation between shrinkage and residual modulus. One percent shrinkage leads to roughly 5% loss in the residual modulus at room temperature.

Fig. 5. Shrinkage vs annealing temperature

Fig. 6. Bending modulus vs shrinkage

Rings from tape or fabric winding

Rings were manufactured according to ASTM D2291 to investigate the feasibility of all-PP wound products either from tape (UD) or fabric winding. Both UD and fabric rings had an internal diameter of 145 mm and a thickness of 1.5 mm.

Apparent hoop tensile properties were determined by the split-disk method (ASTM D2290). Both strength and apparent stiffness were determined as two strain gauges were attached to the rings at the sides [7]. Both the strength (Fig. 7) and the modulus (Fig. 8) results indicate that properties are not influenced when the compaction temperature is raised by 15°C and are 5 (fabric) or 10 (UD) times higher than isotropic PP. This proves that stresses generated in the tape by the mandrel through constraining prevent shrinkage and loss of properties in the hoop direction. However it was noticed that the shrinkage along the tube axis increases with processing temperature.

Fig. 7. Hoop tensile strength of rings

Fig. 8. Hoop tensile modulus of rings

Rectangular tubes from fabric winding

In order to assess the properties along the pipe axis, rectangular tubes (100 x 50 mm cross section) were manufactured at 143°C and 159°C. The wall thickness was 2 mm. Shrinkage along the pipe axis increases as the manufacturing temperature is increased to 159°C (Table 1). The shrinkage along the pipe axis is independent of the cross-section as the same shrinkage was observed for a cylindrical pipe

(Ø 50 mm). As mentioned earlier, the shrinkage corresponds to a reduction in stiffness. The modulus in the axial direction is only two third of the hoop modulus for the pipe consolidated at 159°C. The empirical formula derived from the shrinkage of UD specimens is also valid here: 1% shrinkage corresponds to a 4-5% loss of the modulus. The large temperature processing window and a variable constraining can be used to tailor the stiffness required in the final part.

Table 1. Shrinkage and tensile properties along pipe axis of fabric wound square tubes.

Processing Temperature	Axial Properties		
	Shrinkage	E modulus	Strength
143°C	3.7 %	4.9 ± 0.2 GPa	160 ± 2 MPa
159°C	8.0 %	3.9 ± 0.2 GPa	159 ± 1 MPa

Processing can influence the mechanical properties of oriented polypropylene. This is not a common phenomenon for polymer matrix composites reinforced by glass or carbon fibres. However the empirical relation between shrinkage and stiffness could be a quick and efficient quality control technique for industrial applications.

SHEET PRODUCTION

Sheets are obtained by compacting several layers of all-PP fabric. Six to seven layers of a plain weave fabric are necessary to get a 1 mm thick sheet due to the low nominal weight of the fabric (105 g/m²). All-PP fabrics have to be heated and cooled under constant pressure in order to get optimal properties and compaction. If a standard hot-press were used, cycle times would be too long for any realistic applications. But a continuous process such as belt-press technology (Fig. 9) is suitable to produce sheets from all-PP fabric rolls in spite of a high-investment cost. Isobaric belt-presses usually develop 20-40 bar through heating and cooling. The output speed is in the order of several meters per minute. A compaction temperature of 145°C was found appropriate to get a full compaction.

Fig. 9. Isobaric double belt-press.

The sheets have a modulus of 5.8 GPa and strength of 200 MPa at room temperature for a density of 0.78 g/cm³. There is no significant difference between the warp and the weft directions of the fabric (i.e. along or across the belt direction). The tape strength is strongly dependent on temperature (see Fig. 3). The same dependence is obviously expected for the sheets. Fig. 10 shows the decrease of the tensile strength with temperature between -40°C and 140°C. The shape of the curve between room temperature and 140°C is, as expected, similar to the tape strength dependence on temperature (Fig. 3). The strength at 140°C is nevertheless still higher than isotropic PP strength at room temperature (30 MPa). The stiffness as a function of temperature exhibits a quasi-plateau between -40°C and room temperature with a maximum of 7.2 GPa at -40°C. The modulus degrades then quicker than the strength to reach above 100°C a E-modulus around 1 GPa, equivalent to Isotropic PP at room temperature. Glass Mat Thermoplastics (GMT) and Long Fibre Thermoplastics (LFT), benchmark material in the automotive industry, behave similarly as their temperature dependent properties are dominated by polypropylene behaviour. In the case of all-PP, the loss of stiffness and strength is balanced by an increase in ductility and strain to failure so that the toughness of all-PP is constant

until 80°C (Fig. 12). The higher scatter at -40°C is related to a brittle behaviour of the amorphous phase as the glass transition temperature (T_g) of polypropylene is around -20°C.

Fig. 10. Strength of all-PP sheets as a function of temperature

Fig. 11. Modulus of all-PP sheets as a function of temperature

Fig. 12. Toughness of all-PP sheet as a function of temperature

THERMOFORMING

Applications for flat sheets are rather limited and it is necessary to find an appropriate process to shape the sheets into a final part. A feasible cost-effective route can be based on a non-isothermal stamping process. These all-PP composites are heated in a hot-air oven or infrared heater and subsequently stamped in a cold press.

Stamping from sheets

A straightforward solution lies in heating and stamping a belt-pressed sheet. A study of the thermoforming behaviour of all-PP sheets has shown that different deformation modes are involved compared to glass fabric thermoplastic composites [9]. Domes were stamped from all-PP sheets as well as glass fabric reinforced polypropylene (GF/PP). The deformations were evaluated using the ARAMIS[®] system from GOM, an optical 3D-strain mapping system based on the grating method [10]. Fig. 13 shows the major strain distribution (principal strain ϵ_1) of the inner surface of two domes. One was stamped from a 9 layers all-PP sheet (Fig. 13a) and the other from glass fabric reinforced PP (Fig. 13b). The white lines represent the meridians of the dome that coincide with the principal directions of the fabric (warp and weft directions). The all-PP dome exhibits compressive strains on the pole inner surface compared to GF/PP. The isostrain lines have a star shape due to higher deformations at 45° (Intraply shearing) than along the tape directions. All-PP has a more uniform deformation pattern because of a finer weave style and the limited matrix squeeze flow. Also when forming forces are applied along the tape directions, the tape is drawn and there is no interply shearing which is singular for a multi-layer fabric composite.

Fig. 13. Major strain distribution of the inner surface of an all-PP (a) and a GF/PP (b) dome.

Stamping from fabric stacks

There is an important driving force to avoid the belt-pressing stage as the high investments involved can be detrimental to the cost-effectiveness of thermoplastic composites manufacturing. For that reason, Linecross Ltd (UK) and Queen Mary, University of London develop a stamping process where a stack of fabric is heated and shaped non-isothermally. Using fabric instead of sheets require a higher pressure in order to get a good consolidation in the final part. A lower force to almost close the mould is necessary though as it is sketched on Fig. 14. Another concern, as well, is that the fabric is more sensitive to in-plane wrinkling.

Fig. 14. Stamping force profile during mould closure for sheet and fabric forming

SHORT TAPES COMPOSITES

Short fibre thermoplastics are easier to process than continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastics as they can be either injection or compression moulded. They also represent the largest volume application of glass fibre reinforced polypropylene. In the case of all-PP, advantage in terms of processing is not quite yet the case as the all-PP concept relies on tape welding without much matrix flow. But short tapes all-PP composites could have the potential to cut down the weaving costs. Alternatively all-PP fabric or tape waste could be recycled in short tapes applications as a high-value recycled material. The strength of short fibres composites is given by the following equation [11]:

$$\sigma_{composite} = \eta_{LE} \times \eta_{\theta} \times \sigma_f^* \times V_f \quad (1)$$

Where η_{LE} is the strengthening efficiency of the short fibres and depends on the critical fibre length of the Fibre/Matrix system. η_{θ} is the orientation efficiency which is a purely geometrical factor, V_f , the fibre volume fraction and σ_f^* , the fibre strength. It is important to assess η_{LE} as a function of the tape

length. In order to avoid the influence of η_θ , it was chosen to study short aligned tapes. Cuts at regular intervals (l_t) in the fabric was found an efficient method to produce tensile specimens where 50% of the short tapes are aligned with the direction of testing (Fig. 15). The tape length, l_t , was varied between 9 and 40 mm.

Fig. 15. Short tapes aligned specimens

The strength of these short tapes composites is plotted on Fig. 16. Above 30 mm tape length, a plateau is reached which means that the strengthening efficiency is 1. The maximum strength is half the strength of the continuous all-PP fabric composites. The reason for that being that the tapes were not only aligned but as well regularly arranged so that some singular sections of the specimen (every $l_t/2$) have only 50% reinforcement. A tape length of 9 mm has only a strengthening factor, η_{LE} , of 0.5.

This η_{LE} factor is an important parameter. But it is not yet clear if short tape composites can be processed as cost-effectively as GMT and LFT.

Fig. 16. Short tapes composites strength

Fig. 17. Bending Modulus of all-PP sandwich according to Minimum Weight Criteria

ALL-PP SANDWICH

The rather good mechanical properties of all-PP composites combined with its very low density justify the assessment of the potential of all-PP in structural applications. Sandwich constructions of composites panels display optimised specific bending stiffness and strength. In a sandwich panel, two thin sheets (faces) of a stiff and strong material are separated by a thick core of low-density material. In general, different materials are used for the core and the faces but Eco-design implies that the same material should be used in order to optimise the environmental performance of the product. Polypropylene honeycombs or rigid foams can serve as a core material for truly all-polypropylene sandwich constructions. If the young's modulus of the face is much higher than that of the core ($E_f \gg E_c$) and the face is very thin in relation to the core thickness ($t_f \ll t_c$), then the bending stiffness, D , can be expressed by [12]:

$$D = \frac{1}{2} \times E_f \times b \times t_f \times (s)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$s = t_c + t_f \quad (3)$$

s is the distance between the centres of the two faces and b is the panel width. The stiffness is then independent of the core mechanical properties. The sandwich weight per square unit is:

$$W = 2 \times \rho_f \times t_f + \rho_c \times t_c \quad (4)$$

Kuenzi [13] showed that a minimum weight of specified stiffness is independent of the materials used and the core weight should be twice the weight of the faces.

$$W_c = 2 \times W_f \quad (5)$$

This relation was also verified experimentally by Theulen et Peijs [14]. The optimised bending stiffness per unit width depends only on the core and the face densities and the bending modulus of the face while for a given core material, the weight of the panel per area unit is a linear function of the core thickness.

$$W = \frac{3}{2} \times \rho_c \times t_c \quad (6)$$

The glass reinforced alternative to all-PP composite skins are GMT or glass fabric reinforced polypropylene such as Twintex[®] from Saint Gobain. The density and the bending modulus of these different materials are presented in Table 2. A PP honeycomb with a density of 80 kg/m³ was chosen as the core material. The optimised bending stiffness, D , of each sandwich panel is plotted against the minimum weight and the core thickness on Fig. 17.

Table 2. Bending stiffness and density of polypropylene sandwich face and core material.

Material	Density (kg/m ³)	E modulus (GPa)
PP honeycomb	80	
All-PP	790	4.7
GMT	1140	3.6
Twintex [®] (glass 60%w)	1500	13.0

The behaviour of all-PP as a skin material lies exactly between GMT and Twintex[®] because of its good specific modulus. The all-PP skin is twice as thick as Twintex[®] for a given panel weight because the all-PP density is only half. But the resulting sandwich panel is only 2.6% thicker. It is important to notice that the 3 curves of Fig. 17 are unrealistic, as these thermoplastic composites are not available at any thickness. The weight per square unit of Twintex[®] or all-PP sheets is a multiple of the nominal weight of the fabric. Because all-PP fabric (105 g/m²) is seven times lighter than Twintex[®] fabric (glass content 60%w: 745 g/m²), sandwich panels can be designed closer to the minimum weight criteria. Each cross on Fig. 7 represents the optimum bending stiffness for a given all-PP thickness.

CONCLUSION

- Light all-polypropylene composites can be processed by several processing routes in a similar way to glass reinforced composites: tape winding, thermoforming either from plates or directly from fabric stacks.
- The simple tape or fabric winding technique can be used to make pipes or pressure vessels with tensile properties up to ten times higher than isotropic PP. Because both matrix and reinforcement are derived from the same bulk material, the mechanical properties of the oriented phase can be degraded during processing. But this degradation can be estimated by the shrinkage along the reinforcement direction and by controlling this effect, properties on the final product can be tailored.
- Woven fabrics are belt-pressed into plates. Their tensile properties were found to be strongly dependent on the temperature. These plates can be thermoformed into shell products. Although the overall mode of deformation is intraply shearing, no interply shearing but tape drawing is observed when forming forces are applied along the reinforcement direction.
- A cost-effective alternative is to stamp directly from heated fabric layers in order to avoid the costly belt-pressing stage for the manufacturing of semi-finished sheets.
- A tape length higher than 20 mm is required to get a high strengthening efficiency in case of short tapes composites. However because matrix flow is limited, all-PP short tape composites may not have the clear advantage of flow moulding materials like GMT or LFT required for moulding complex shapes.
- The low density of all-PP sheets in addition to a low fabric weight per unit square raises the potential of all-PP as a face material in 100% polypropylene sandwich construction. The core material can be either PP rigid foam or honeycomb.

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